

NEW VIEW ON THE FAMILY BUSINESS SUCCESS FACTORS ANALYSIS FOR THE INDUSTRY 4.0 ENVIRONMENT

NOVI POGLED NA ANALIZU FAKTORA USPEHA ZA PORODIČNE FIRME U OKRUŽENJU INDUSTRIJE 4.0

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Apstrakt: Ovaj rad analizira faktore uspeha porodičnih preduzeća (PP), fokusirajući se na sistemsko razmišljanje, organizacione mreže i nove pristupe u veštačkoj inteligenciji i analizi podataka. Očekuje se da će PP ostati važan faktor u globalnoj ekonomiji uprkos permakriznom i polikriznom okruženju. Da bi se poboljšao njihov uspeh, može se primeniti mnoštvo faktora. Autori su se fokusirali na analizu sistemskog razmišljanja, organizacionih mreža i veštačke inteligencije /analitike podataka. Rezultati su zasnovani na analizi literature i konsultantskom iskustvu autora. Uvidi autora su sintetizovani u tabeli na kraju članka. Tabela sa predloženim faktorima upoređuje osobine dugovečnosti uspeha PP: dugoročna orijentacija, prilagođavanje bez gubitka identiteta, jak sistem nasleđivanja, uključivanje zajednice, inkluzivne strukture upravljanja i specijalizacija uloga i profesionalizacija. U preseku tabele je predložen konkretan skup akcija za implementaciju.

Ključne reči: Porodične firme, kritični faktori uspeha, sistemsko razmišljanje, organizacione društvene mreže, veštačka inteligencija.

Abstract: This paper analyses success factors of family-owned businesses (FOBs), focusing on systems thinking, organizational networks and recently advanced data/AI analytics. FOBs are expected to remain an important factor in global economy despite the permacrisis and polycrisis environment. To improve their success, a multitude of factors can be applied. Authors have focused on analysis of Systems Thinking (ST), Organizational Social Networks (OSN), and Artificial Intelligence (AI)/data analytics. Results are based on literature analysis and the author's consulting experience. Authors' insights are synthesized in the table at the end of the article. The table crosses FOB's longevity success traits: long-term orientation, adaptation without losing identity, strong intergenerational succession, community embedding, inclusive governance structures and role specialization and professionalization with the proposed factors. A concrete set of actions for implementation is proposed in the cross section of the table.

Keywords: Family-owned businesses, Critical Success Factors, Systems Thinking, Organizational Social Networks, Artificial Intelligence

1. INTRODUCTION

This article presents a literature analysis and synthesis of qualitative empirical insights into the critical success factors (CSFs) for family-owned businesses (FOBs) through the lenses of systems thinking, organizational networking, and AI/data analytics. FOBs are defined as “business governed and/or managed with the intention to sustain family control across generations, where family members hold significant ownership and/or management roles, and family involvement influences the firm’s strategic direction and values”. (Chua, Chrisman & Sharma, 1999). Family firms account for roughly two-thirds of all businesses worldwide and around 70% of global GDP (UNCTAD, 2021). Their contribution to the global economy, characterized by their long-term orientation, strong identity rooted in family legacy, and deep community ties (Miller & Le Breton-Miller, 2005), significantly impacts the social, ecological, and economic environments. Characterized by resilience, many of the world’s oldest continuously operating companies are FOBs. At the same time, family businesses face challenges that remain largely unchanged for decades, even centuries. Even in the Industry 4.0 environment, family firms continue to balance continuity and change across generations (Miller & Le Breton-Miller, 2005; De Massis et al., 2016), but new approaches are still required. On the other hand, some FOBs cannot keep up with the new environment, as only about 30% of FOBs remain in family hands by the second generation and fewer than 15% into the third (Gersick et al., 1997). This article describes a new way to analyze critical factors which support success, resilience, and longevity of FOBs as they innovate and adapt to new business realities.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

According to previous research, the oldest FOBs share the following characteristics which underscore family dynamics and relationships: (1) a long-term strategic horizon, (2) an ability to adapt without losing their core identity, (3) effective intergenerational succession planning, (4) deep community embedding and stakeholder trust, (5) robust governance structures balancing family and business interests, and (6) role diversification that professionalizes management (Miller & Le Breton-Miller, 2005; Berrone et al., 2012; De Massis et al., 2016). Each of these factors is both important for family business traditions and crucial for embracing novelty and innovation. For example, a long-term orientation can justify investing in sustainable innovation with rewards gained later in the future. Strong family identity can be leveraged to adopt new initiatives based on and supporting legacy and values (Berrone et al., 2012). However, this can be possible only if the family’s internal culture, relationships, and communication allow new ideas to be shared and accepted. Rigid traditions and intergenerational misunderstandings can turn these strengths into conflicts and inflexibility, creating systemic “traps” (Meadows, 2008) that hinder renewal. For this reason, it is necessary to keep in mind that managing FOBs

is usually conditioned by complex interactions shaped by family ties, power structures, and cultural context.

2.1 FOB'S SUCCESS FACTORS

Topics such as adopting digital technologies, engaging in open innovation, and implementing Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) practices have become an important field of research for better understanding FOBs (De Massis et al., 2016; Gupta & Levenburg, 2010). Many family enterprises are aware that such innovations are necessary for maintaining their competitive advantage. However, studies reveal that despite their stable financial wealth and long-term orientation, family firms often lag in adopting disruptive innovations and formal sustainability practices (Gómez-Mejía et al., 2007; De Massis et al., 2013). One of the main causes is the desire to preserve socio-emotional wealth (SEW), the family's non-financial legacy and control, which often leads to risk aversion (Gómez-Mejía et al., 2007). Furthermore, paternalistic leadership, often characteristic for FOBs, centralizes authority and limits bottom-up initiatives, creating succession bottlenecks where the outgoing generation resists the incoming generation's new ideas (Handler, 1990). Entrenched informal networks in family firms, often expressed through loyalty-based relationships of the inner circle of confidantes, can further reinforce those patterns. However, while these tight networks are a source of strength, they may block the inflow of external knowledge and impede organizational learning and openness to change (Zahra, 2010). The combination of FOBs' internal relationship dynamics, its external context, and cultural characteristics has a critical influence on its attitude towards innovation. National and regional cultural impact on the way business is conducted has gained attention in business studies in general. Their role in understanding FOBs dynamics appears to be significant. For instance, in high collectivist or high power-distance cultures, deference to elders and tradition in family firms can impact how new practices are evaluated (Gupta & Levenburg, 2010).

The ownership stage of a family enterprise, whether it is founder-led, a sibling partnership, or a multi-family cousin consortium (Gersick et al., 1997), presents different structural challenges and plays an important role in how novelties are accepted and adopted. Founder-controlled firms can act decisively under a visionary founding leader but may heavily depend on his or her support for introducing any major innovation. Sibling- or cousin-owned firms, on the other hand, need more complex governance and depend on the consensus among branches of an extended family, which can slow decision-making process or create inertia regarding strategic changes (Lansberg & Astrachan, 1994). Later-generation family firms often formalize governance through boards and professional managers, which can either facilitate innovation by bringing in outside perspectives or, if mismanaged, add bureaucracy. Based on the aforementioned, it can be concluded that any kind of innovation adoption strongly depends on cultural characteristics, generational stages, and environmental conditions. This reinforces the importance of studying FOB dynamics across multiple levels, from macro environmental

circumstances, meso industry-level trends, to micro interpersonal relationships. In recent years scholars have begun to understand that it takes more than assessing static parameters to understand FOBs' behavior, and it needs to introduce dynamic perspective to captures how processes evolve in time (Salvato & Aldrich, 2012). One of the solutions was to use those behavioral theories which can help analyze complex interactions in family firms. Table 1 represents four commonly used theories, and their limitations.

Table 1: Limitations of behavioral theories used for analyzing FOBs

Theory	Description	Limitations
Agency theory (Jensen & Meckling, 1976)	How ownership alignment mitigates owner-manager conflicts	No explanation why emotional aspects are stronger than economic logic
Resource-based view (RBV) (Barney, 1991)	Identifies unique resources that support competitive advantage	Inward-looking, static
Socio-emotional wealth (SEW) (Gómez-Mejía et al., 2007)	Decision making motives for non-financial goals	No explanation of underlying processes how decisions develop over time through organization
Institutional theory (Di Maggio & Powell, 1983)	How company responds to external pressures and influences	Treats company as a homogeneous entity, underemphasizes internal family interactions
Theory of Planned Behavior (Ajzen, 1991)	Key decision-makers attitudes, influence, and capabilities	Not an integrative approach

Source: Author's synthesis of reviewed literature.

The most used methodologies for analyzing family dynamics and how they impact FOBs strategic decisions are surveys and case studies which provide both qualitative and quantitative insights (Eddleston et al., 2012). Investments in research and development (R&D) and innovation, adoption of innovation, and return on investments and earnings from innovation, are subjects that were largely studied and compared among family and non-family companies. The results show that FOBs are more cautious when it comes to investing in structured R&D and adoption of radical innovations (De Massis et al., 2013). However, the variance is high, suggesting that contingent factors are important. Furthermore, cross-sectional analyses struggle to capture trends over time and self-correcting feedback. There are several models which are used for the analysis of the adoption of new technologies, such as the Technology Adoption Model (TAM) and Diffusion of Innovations Theory (DOI), along with behavioral theories like the Theory of Planned Behavior. However, DOI which highlights that communication channels, social influence, and time influence innovation adoption (Rogers, 1962), and behavioral approach focuses more on the attitudes, influence, and capabilities of the key decision-maker (Ajzen, 1991) are lacking an integrative approach that can simultaneously analyze relationships and dynamic feedback within a structure. That highlights the need for holistic, systems-oriented frameworks which would help to understand the evolution of FOBs.

2.2 SYSTEMS THINKING

Understanding system dynamics can help resolve problems that are not easily solvable by using linear solutions, especially when we consider the interconnected social and environmental challenges of today's world. Recognizing that organizations are complex systems, with integrative effect, can show how issues are connected and help design sustainable, long-term responses across fields (Forliano et al., 2024).

In organizational research, systems thinking helps by uncovering how policies or events can produce counter-intuitive outcomes through feedback processes. It is often visualized through causal loop diagrams or simulated through system dynamics equations (Sterman, 2000). When it comes to FOBs context, a system dynamics model might represent how resources allocated to an innovation project creates a reinforcing feedback loop or balancing feedback. ST explains why certain patterns occur. It formalizes hypotheses about causality and identifies leverage points, places in the system where a small change can have a large effect, crucial for the intervention.

However, a pure systems thinking approach in management often ignores the specifics of individuals. Classic system dynamics models often use aggregate variables such as knowledge stock or innovation adoption rate and may overlook the heterogeneity of members of an organization. To provide details about who is involved in those feedback loops, a complementary perspective becomes necessary.

2.3 ORGANISATIONAL SOCIAL NETWORKS

The organizational social network (OSN) perspective focuses on the relationships among actors, including both individuals and units. It explains how these network structures influence information flow, power, and innovation (Borgatti & Foster, 2003). In family businesses, OSNs often have unique configurations. Family members typically occupy central nodes in both formal and informal networks, with multilayered and interconnected ties, as family members can be connected as relatives, co-workers, and owners simultaneously. Social network analysis (SNA) provides metrics like centrality, structural holes, brokerage, and network density or clustering (Borgatti & Foster, 2003; Cross & Parker, 2004). Studies suggest that network properties significantly affect innovation in organizations, so diverse, open networks support and stimulate creativity and knowledge recombination. On the other hand, closed, insular networks may reinforce the status quo (Granovetter, 1973; Uzzi, 1997). In FOBs, informal networks often carry more weight than formal structures. Therefore, mapping these influence networks is crucial to understanding how innovations internally diffuse. In studies about family firms, OSN has been relatively limited with a tendency to grow. For instance, Sorenson et al. (2009) examine how social capital, including trust, norms, and networks within family firms, facilitate or hinder knowledge sharing. Zahra (2010) researched how

external networks could help family SMEs overcome resource constraints and adopt new ideas. OSN view highlights “who matters” and “who talks to whom” which could help understand where resistance or support for an innovation originates. In FOBs systems, examples are a group of long-term employees who are resisting changing or adopting a new process, or an influential cousin promoting a change. On its own, however, OSN analysis is often structural and static. It provides a picture of relationships at a given point in time and is typically descriptive rather than causal. Without dynamics in time dimension, it might reveal the current pattern of communication, but not how it evolves in different circumstances, as for example in a succession phase.

Considering all the above, neither a pure system nor a pure network approach alone can provide a comprehensive picture of the family firm dynamics, especially of complex processes such as innovation adoption or succession. ST can model dynamic complexity but also tends to treat the organization as a “black box” or focus extensively on aggregate levels. To the contrary, SNA opens this “black box” to reveal structural complexity but often freezes time or omits the feedback loops that drive change. Therefore, integrating ST and OSN can connect the “why” with the “who” and “how”. ST explains why certain patterns occur by examining causation over time, while OSN pinpoints who is involved in and affected by those patterns and helps understand how it all takes place in the wider organizational context. Recent research in other domains supports the idea of such integration. In public health and epidemiology, scholars have combined system dynamics models with network analysis to study the spread of diseases and health behaviors through social systems, capturing both disease transmission feedback loops and the social network structures that channel infections or information (Whelan et al., 2023). These interdisciplinary examples demonstrate that combining dynamic modeling with network analysis yields richer insights into complex adaptive systems.

However, in the family business field, few if any studies have explicitly integrated ST and OSN approaches to date. Historically, part of the reason is the disciplinary silos. System dynamics and ST both have roots in management science and organizational learning (e.g. Senge, 1990), whereas OSN research emerged from sociology and organizational behavior. Researchers traditionally showed a tendency to specialize either in one approach or the other, and the technical challenges made integration rather difficult. Until recently, the data requirements to feed both a network model and a system model synchronously were hard to meet. ST models relied on informal, qualitative, or aggregate data, while mapping an organizational network required labor-intensive surveys or communication data that were not readily available in real-time.

These barriers are starting to erode with advances in technology and data analytics, most notably the advent of digital traces and AI techniques that can continuously capture and analyze organizational dynamics. Artificial Intelligence (AI) can play an enabling role in bridging systems and networks by handling the scale, speed, and complexity of data characteristics for modern organizations. With most businesses utilizing digital tools,

data can be mined both ethically and securely, to capture and understand network structures and performance indicators. Graph neural networks and dynamic network analytics enable organizational social networks to be updated in near real-time from communication data, revealing how interaction patterns change. Similarly, AI-based causal discovery algorithms can help identify feedback loops or causal relationships from observational data, strengthening the quantitative underpinnings of system dynamics models (Glymour et al., 2019). AI can also facilitate simulation and scenario analysis. Once an integrated model (ST-OSN) is built, AI can rapidly simulate thousands of “what-if” scenarios or optimize for certain outcomes. In short, AI functions could serve as a “connective tissue” in an integrated framework, linking the structural (network) and dynamic (system) elements and keeping the model updated with real-world data. Even with the study conducted by Nguyen and Welch (2025) critically examining the use of GenAI in qualitative research, showing that while LLMs promise efficiency, their uncritical adoption risks undermining the inherently human task of interpreting meaning, we still believe that their further development will enhance their core features.

3. PRELIMINARY RESULTS AND CONCLUSION

A summarized guideline of how FOBs CSFs could be analyzed using ST-OSN approach is presented in Table 2.

Table 2: FOBs’ success factors analyzed through ST-OSN-AI lens

Longevity Success Factor	Systems Thinking Lens (Macro-Dynamics)	Organizational Network Lens (Micro-Structure)	Modern AI/Data Analytics Support
Long-term orientation	Models delayed feedback loops (e.g. <i>invest now</i> → <i>benefits decades later</i>) that sustain innovation through downturns. (Senge, 1990)	Transmits shared values and vision across generations via dense family networks, reinforcing patience and commitment.	AI-driven simulation of long-range scenarios (e.g. ESG ROI over 20+ years) to inform strategic planning.
Adaptation without losing identity	Captures the balancing loops between tradition and change, showing how excessive conservatism versus radical change impacts firm survival. (Meadows, 2008)	Identifies key brokers between the “old guard” and innovators, enabling knowledge flow without alienating the elders (Sorenson, 2009)	NLP analysis of internal communications to detect effective value-based “framing” of innovations (aligning novelty with legacy).
Strong intergenerational succession	Represents succession as feedback loops (reinforcing if a capable successor drives growth; balancing if uncertainty slows momentum).	Maps the emerging influence of next-generation members in the informal network (e.g., rising centrality of a successor in advice networks).	AI-based sentiment and network analysis to forecast succession outcomes (e.g., flagging if a successor lacks support in key sub-units).

Longevity Success Factor	Systems Thinking Lens (Macro-Dynamics)	Organizational Network Lens (Micro-Structure)	Modern AI/Data Analytics Support
Community embedding	Highlights reinforcing loops between reputation and stakeholder loyalty (e.g. goodwill → customer loyalty → stability), underscoring social capital.	This text maps external ties to the community, customers, and regulators, revealing how family firm networks reach into the broader ecosystem.	Sentiment analysis on social media and stakeholder feedback to gauge community trust in real time.
Inclusive governance structures	Models governance “pressure-release” loops (e.g. family council deliberations preventing broader conflict), ensuring viability.	Uncovers hidden coalitions or factions via network modularity (e.g. detecting if non-family executives are isolated from decision networks).	AI detection of emerging silos or polarization (e.g., via Email network analysis) prompts timely governance interventions.
Role specialization and professionalization	Frames a balancing loop of delegation vs. control (too much centralized control creates bottlenecks, too little harms cohesion).	Reveals role clusters (owners vs. managers vs. outside experts) and information flow between them, highlighting integration gaps.	Organizational network analytics to monitor collaboration patterns as the firm professionalizes (e.g. identifying if new professional managers are properly embedded).

Source: Author’s synthesis of reviewed literature.

Based on the findings from the literature review and practice, we can conclude that an integrative Systems Thinking and Organizational Network (ST–OSN) approach, enhanced by modern data analytics, has strong potential to overcome limitations of prior methods in family business research. It analyses complex realities of family firms, where outcomes are the product of iterative feedback and interpersonal relations unfolding over time. Furthermore, the proposed framework can help identify which “leverage points” in terms of people or processes can be targeted to improve the chance of successful change, thus providing both explanatory power and practical insights. While ST-ON is promising in scope, it has several limitations, including the possible complexity of implementation, high data and skill demands, privacy concerns, semantic misinterpretation, and difficulty in capturing emotions. These challenges make modular application, human validation, and selective use critical for adoption. Future research could reinforce this framework by including longitudinal empirical studies and cross-cultural comparisons. This approach would help testing the proposed integrated framework in diverse and dynamic family business contexts and identifying how cultural, generational, and industry-specific factors may influence its effectiveness.

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